

THE ETYMOLOGY OF ENGLISH WORDS

Zilola Shuxrat qizi Mahmudova

Master student of Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region

Muhabbat Anatolyevna Yusupova

PhD of Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region

ABSTRACT

It is well known that languages evolve over the centuries and words undergo changes. In fact, it is nearly impossible to find a word in English language that has not undergone any changes at all. From my point of view, I have tried to elaborate some of the words and their etymology in this article. The article certainly does not include all the words of English but is meant to serve the purpose of understanding a little about the etymology of words.

Keywords: international words, etymological doublets, structural elements of borrowings, translation-loan.

INTRODUCTION

Etymology is the study of the history of words, their origins and how their form and meaning have changed over time.

It is true that English vocabulary, which is one of the most extensive among the world's languages contains an immense number of words of foreign origin. Explanations for this should be sought in the history of the language which is closely connected with the history of the nation speaking the language.

METHODOLOGY

The first century B.C. Most of the territory now known to us as Europe was occupied by the Roman Empire. Among the inhabitants of the Europe are Germanic tribes. Theirs stage of development was rather primitive, especially if compared with the high civilization of Rome. They are primitive cattle-breeders and know almost

nothing about land cultivation. Their tribal languages contain only Indo-European and Germanic elements.

Due to Roman invasion Germanic tribes had to come into contact with Romans. Romans built roads, bridges, military camps. Trade is carried on, and the Germanic people gain knowledge of new and useful things. The first among them are new things to eat. It has been mentioned that Germanic cattle-breeding was on a primitive scale. Its only products known to the Germanic tribes were meat and milk. It is from the Romans that they learn how to make butter and cheese and, as there are naturally no words for these foodstuffs in their tribal languages, they had to use the Latin words to name them (Lat. “butyrum”, “caseus”). It is also to the Romans that the Germanic tribes owe the knowledge of some new fruits and vegetables of which they had no idea before, and the Latin names of these fruits and vegetables entered their vocabularies: “cherry” (Lat. “cerasum”), “pear” (Lat. “pirum”), “plum” (Lat. “prunus”), “pea” (Lat. “pisum”), “beet” (Lat. “beta”), “pepper” (Lat. “piper”). Here are some more examples of Latin borrowings of this period: “cup” (Lat. “cuppa”), “kitchen” (Lat. “coquina”), “mill” (Lat. “molina”), “port” (Lat. “portus”), “wine” (Lat. “vinum”).

Latin words became the earliest group of borrowings in the future English language which was much later built on the basis of the Germanic tribal languages.

The fifth century A.D. Several of the Germanic tribes (the most numerous among them were the Angles, the Saxons and the Jutes) migrated across the sea to the British Isles. There they were confronted by the Celts, the original inhabitants of the Isles. The Celts desperately defended their lands against the invaders, but nevertheless gradually yielded most of their territory. They retreated to the North and South-West (modern Scotland, Wales and Cornwall). Through numerous contacts with the defeated Celts, the conquerors borrowed a number of Celtic words (bald, down, glen, bard, cradle). Especially numerous among the Celtic borrowings were place names, names of rivers, hills, etc. The Germanic tribes occupied the land, but the names of many parts of their territory remained Celtic. For instance, the names of the rivers Avon, Exe, Esk, Usk, Ux originate from Celtic words meaning

"river" and "water". Ironically, even the name of the English capital originates from Celtic "Llyn+dun" in which "llyn" is another Celtic word for "river" and "dun" stands for "a fortified hill" the meaning of the whole is "fortress on the hill over the river".

Some Latin words entered the Anglo-Saxon languages through Celtic, among them such widely used words as "street" (Lat. *strata via*) and "wall" (Lat. *vallum*).

It was quite natural that educational terms were also Latin borrowings, for the first schools in England were church schools, and the first teachers priests and monks. So, the very word "school" is a Latin borrowing (Lat. *schola*, of Greek origin) and so are such words as "scholar" (Lat. *Scholar(-is)*) and "magister" (Lat. *magister*). From the end of the 8th century to the middle of the 11th century England underwent several Scandinavian invasions. Here are some examples of early Scandinavian borrowings: *call (v.), take (v.), cast (v.), die (v.), law (n.), husband (n.), window (n.), ill (adj.), loose, (adj.), low (adj.), weak (adj.)*. Some of Scandinavian borrowings are easily recognizable by the initial (sk-) combination. E. g. *sky, skill, skin, ski, skirt*.

The Norman culture of the 11th century was certainly superior to that of the Saxons. The result was that English vocabulary acquired a great number of French words. But instead of being smashed and broken by the powerful intrusion of the foreign element, the English language managed to preserve its essential structure and vastly enriched its expressive resources with the new borrowings. England became a bilingual country, and the impact on the English vocabulary made over this two-hundred-years period is immense: French words from the Norman dialect penetrated every aspect of social life. Here is a very brief list of examples of Norman French borrowings.

Administrative words: *state, government, parliament, council, power*.

Legal terms: *court, judge, justice, crime, prison*.

Military terms: *army, war, soldier, officer, battle, enemy*.

Educational terms: *pupil, lesson, library, science, pen, pencil*.

Terms of everyday life: *table, plate, dinner, supper, river, autumn, uncle, etc*.

The historical survey above shows the ways in which English vocabulary developed and of the major events through which it acquired its vast modern resources. Considering the high percentage of borrowed words, one would have to classify English as a language of international origin or, at least, a Romance one (as French and Latin words obviously prevail). But here another factor comes into play: the native element in English comprises a large number of high frequency words like the articles, prepositions, pronouns, conjunctions, auxiliaries and, also, words denoting everyday objects and ideas (e. g. house, child, water, go, come, eat, good, bad, etc.).

Furthermore, the grammatical structure is essentially Germanic and it remains unaffected by foreign influence. By the Indo-European element are meant words of roots common to all (or most) languages of the Indo-European group. The words of this group denote elementary concepts without which no human communication would be possible. The following groups can be identified.

1. Family relations: *father, mother, brother, son, daughter.*
2. Parts of the human body: *foot, nose, lip, heart.*
3. Animals: *cow, swine, goose.*
4. Plants: *tree, birch, corn.*
5. Time of day: *day, night.*
6. Heavenly bodies: *sun, moon, star.*
7. Numerous adjectives: *red, new, glad, sad.*
8. The numerals from one to a hundred.
9. Pronouns - personal (except “*they*” which is a Scandinavian borrowing) and demonstrative.
10. Numerous verbs: *be, stand, sit, eat, know.*

The Germanic element represents words of roots common to all or most Germanic languages. Some of the main groups of Germanic words are the same as in the Indo-European element.

1. Parts of the human body: *head, hand, arm, finger, bone.*
2. Animals: *bear, fox, calf.*
3. Plants: *oak, fir, grass.*
4. Natural phenomena: *rain, frost.*
5. Seasons of the year: *winter, spring, summer.*
6. Landscape features: *sea, land.*
7. Human dwellings and furniture: *house, room, bench.*
8. Sea-going vessels: *boat, ship.*
9. Adjectives: *green, blue, grey, white, small, thick, high, old, good.*
10. Verbs: *see, hear, speak, tell, say, answer, make, give, drink.*

Structural elements of borrowings

There are certain structural features which enable us to identify some words as borrowings and even to determine the source language. We have already established that the initial usually indicates Scandinavian origin. We can also recognize words of Latin and French origin by certain suffixes, prefixes or endings. Here are some typical and frequent structural elements of Latin and French borrowings:

Latin affixes of nouns:

The suffix (-ion): *legion, opinion, etc.*; the suffix (-tion): *relation, temptation, etc.*

Latin affixes of verbs:

The suffix (-ate): *appreciate, create, congratulate, etc.*; the suffix (-ute): *attribute, distribute, etc.*; the remnant suffix (-ct): *act, collect, conduct, etc.*; the prefix (dis-): *disable, disagree, etc.*

Latin affixes of adjectives:

The suffix (-able): *detestable, curable, etc.*; the suffix (-ate): *accurate, graduate, etc.*; the suffix (-ant): *important, etc.*; the suffix (-ent): *absent, evident, etc.*; the suffix (-or): *major, senior, etc.*; the suffix (-al): *final, maternal, etc.*; the suffix (-ar): *solar, familiar, etc.*

It's important to note that later formations derived from native roots borrowed Latin and French affixes (e.g. eatable, lovable).

International Words

It is often the case that a word is borrowed by several languages, not just by one. Such words usually convey concepts which are significant in the field of communication. Many of them are of Latin and Greek origin. Most names of sciences are international (e. g. philosophy, mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology, medicine, linguistics, lexicology). There are also numerous terms of art in this group: music, theatre, drama, tragedy, comedy, artist, primadonna, etc.; and the sports terms: football, volleyball, baseball, hockey, cricket, rugby, tennis, golf, etc. It is quite natural that political terms frequently occur in the international group of borrowings: politics, policy, revolution, progress, democracy, communism, anti-militarism. 20th century scientific and technological advances brought a great number of new international words: atomic, antibiotic, radio, television, sputnik (a Russian borrowing). Fruits and foodstuffs imported from exotic countries often transport their names too and become international: coffee, cocoa, chocolate, banana, mango, avocado, grapefruit.

The similarity of such words as the English “son”, the German “Sohn” and the Russian “сын” should not lead one to the quite false conclusion that they are international words. They represent the Indo-European group of the native element in each respective language and are cognates, i. e. words of the same etymological root, and not borrowings.

Etymological Doublets

The words originating from the same etymological source, but differing in phonemic shape and in meaning are called etymological doublets. They may enter the vocabulary by different routes. Some of these pairs consist of a native word and a borrowed word: “shrew”, n. (E.) – “screw”, n. (Sc.). Others are represented by two borrowings from different languages: “canal” (Lat.) - “channel” (Fr.), “captain”

(Lat.) — “chieftain” (Fr.). Still others were borrowed from the same language twice, but in different periods: “travel” (Norm. Fr.) - “travail” (Par. Fr.), “cavalry” (Norm. Fr.) - “chivalry” (Par. Fr.), “gaol” (Norm. Fr.) - “jail” (Par. Fr.).

Translation-Loans

By translation-loans we indicate borrowings of a special kind. They are not taken into the vocabulary of another language more or less in the same phonemic shape in which they have been functioning in their own language, but undergo the process of translation. It is quite obvious that it is only compound words (i. e. words of two or more stems). Each stem was translated separately: “masterpiece” (from Germ. “Meisterstück”), “wonder child” (from Germ. “Wunderkind”), “first dancer” (from Ital. “prima-ballerina”).

In point of comparing the expressive and stylistic value of the French and the English words the French ones are usually more formal, more refined, and less emotional. “to begin” – “to commence”, “to wish” — “to desire”, “happiness” — “felicity”.

English words are much warmer than their Latin synonyms, they don’t sound cold and dry: “motherly” — “maternal”, “fatherly” — “paternal”, “childish” — “infantile”, “daughterly” — “filial”, etc.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

As a result, the etymology of English words is very broad and has been formed over the years. German language has adopted the translational loan from English-speaking nations that became familiar with the very notion of skyscrapers earlier due to the emergence of this technological breakthrough in their territory.

From this illustration, it becomes clear that loan translations are the phenomenon that takes place when the loan item is a composite form in the upper language and the borrower creates a parallel composite structure from one’s language material.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be pointed out that the evidence shows that when two languages come into contact with each other, the language shift situations will occur including lexical and phonetic borrowings. Language contact takes place in situations in which groups of different languages speakers interact such as colonization, migration, performing trade or occupying new lands inhabited by other nations. As a result of language contact, speakers of one language adopt words from speakers of another language that is referred to as the source language. Such words are qualified by linguists as loan words or borrowings.

REFERENCES

1. Stockwell, Robert & Minkova, Donka. "English Words: History and Structure" Cambridge University Press, 2001 Print
2. List, Johann-Mattis. "Networks of Lexical Borrowing and Lateral Gene Transfer in Language and Genome Evolution." *BioEssays* 36.2 (2014): 141-150. Print.
3. Sapir, Edward. *Language*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014. Print.
4. Kemmer, Suzanne. "Loanwords." *Words in English*. Web.